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Engaging & supporting EU experts in Cybersecurity Standardisation activities

Standardisation for the Cyber Resilience Act

**CYBERSTAND
ONLINE WEBINAR**
26th February 2025

Post-Event report

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For professionals involved in EU cybersecurity, understanding the implications of the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) and the standardisation request is not just beneficial, but essential for shaping the security of their digital products.

This webinar will bring you bang up to date with the current status of the CRA and progress on how the European Standardisation Organisations are responding to the much anticipated Standardisation Request. This will include information on the Working Groups relevant to the CRA and the timeline for the implementation of both horizontal and vertical standards. We'll hear from the key players in this process including Filipe Jones-Mourao, Cybersecurity & Digital Privacy Policy at DG Connect, and Lucia Lanfri, CEN-CENELEC.

With the current focus on the drafting and consensus building of the horizontal standards cited in the draft SReq, the webinar will also highlight related events planned by the Danish National Standardisation Body DANSK in the frame of the STAN4CR EU-funded project. The event will also provide information on how European stakeholders can access funding to contribute to the development of standards in this area through the CYBERSTAND.eu's 4th Specific Service Procedure.

Event Takeaways:

The webinar emphasizes the importance of collaboration between multiple EU-funded projects to support and streamline contributions to cybersecurity standardization, particularly in relation to the Cyber Resilience Act.

One of the key innovations of the CRA is that essential requirements cover the entire product lifecycle — not just design and development, but also the period after the product is placed on the market. Manufacturers must continue to monitor and ensure the product remains secure throughout its use.

Developed European Standards automatically replace conflicting national standards under the “standstill rule.” This mechanism is essential to the functioning of the European Single Market, promoting alignment and consistency. The process is firmly rooted in consensus and reflects a harmonized and collaborative approach.

The Copenhagen workshop held on 8 April was part of a wider initiative under the STAN4CR project, funded by the European Commission. Similar workshops will also take place in Spain and Cyprus later in the year, engaging stakeholders, including industry professionals and businesses, in the standardization process, ensuring broad support and collaboration.

Manufacturers must conduct a continuous and systematic risk assessment throughout the product’s lifecycle — from design and development to maintenance — to ensure that their products meet the CRA’s essential cybersecurity requirements. Based on the outcome of the risk analysis, manufacturers may also need to implement additional controls beyond those explicitly listed in the CRA, to appropriately address identified risks and ensure conformity.

Cyberstand is particularly interested in bringing new voices into the standardization process — domain experts, SMEs, and open-source contributors — to help diversify and strengthen participation.

Insights from the experts:

“One way in which you can contribute to the standards is by applying to Cyberstand... we’re very interested in funding, you know, people who perhaps aren’t currently involved. So if you’re a domain expert, you have knowledge in this field, but you don’t already contribute to standards then you can apply for this”

Nicholas Ferguson

(HSbooster and CYBERSTAND coordinator and Trust-IT Services)

“When we are developing standards for the CRA we are also developing the infrastructure that will allow the supply chain to communicate across each of its stages, so it starts from microchips all the way up to large hardware products”

Filipe Jones-Mourão

(Cybersecurity & Digital Privacy Policy, DG CONNECT, European Commission)

“That’s how we work: actually we are based on the national delegation principle, representing a consensus. Of course, standards are voluntary, so this is not a mandatory thing that we do and we are constantly in dialogue with the national bodies to try to have the consensus, the represented view, of everyone.”

Lucia Lanfri

(Project Manager Electrotechnology Standardization and Digital Solutions - CEN/CENELEC)

“The main objective of our workshop is to present the preliminary content of the horizontal standards being developed to comply with lines 1 and 15 in the standardization request, and then to receive feedback and input from stakeholders that are going to comply with the Cyber Resilience Act.”

Berit Aadal (Chief Consultant -Danish Standards)

“The Cyber Resilience Act is basically a market placement legislation primarily, but not only, because it also provides for obligations that need to be fulfilled even after market placement. The scope of the products is huge, it encompasses all products with digital elements, hardware and software including components and remote data processing solutions “

Maria Raphael (Funded Expert of CYBERSTAND.eu SSP1)

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Watch the recording!

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